

EOSC-Life: Building a digital space for the life sciences

D6.3 — FAIRsharing webpage

WP6 – FAIRification and Provenance Services

Lead Beneficiary: BBMRI and ERINHA/INSERM

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Contributing partner(s): UOXF for WP6, and EMBL-EBI, ELIXIR, Fraunhofer and EU-OPENSOURCE for WP1

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Executive Summary

FAIRsharing¹ has been selected by WP1 as the project's registry of data resources and standards that are part of and used by research infrastructures in EOSC-Life. This deliverable summarises the work of WP6 to deliver a FAIRsharing Collection of these data resources (and associated standards) to ensure these resources are Findable (e.g. discoverable and citable via a DOI), Accessible (e.g. access methods to their data is clearly described), Interoperable (e.g. standards implemented are declared) and Re-usable (e.g. terms of use of the data are made explicit to users). This work is described in detail in D1.2² and D1.3³, and the EOSC-Life FAIRsharing Collection of 133 records (as of Aug 2022) is publicly available⁴. As this is a live view of the EOSC-Life resource ecosystem, a variety of stages of the resource life cycle are displayed. In-development, Ready and Deprecated resources are marked as such allowing users to assess their relevance. In Jan 2022 a newly improved FAIRsharing backend and frontend was also released by the UOXF partner, who also runs and curates the registry. This new version is set to improve the discoverability of and the relationships among the resources, and also offers new RI-centric pages (e.g. ELIXIR⁵ and MIRRI⁶). These pages enable attribution at the level of the RIs and the responsible individuals themselves. Each RI page in FAIRsharing showcases its associated repositories, standards and collections and identifies and attributes (via ORCID) related users. The records in the EOSC-Life FAIRsharing Collection are a part of the wider FAIRsharing registry, which is computationally accessible to a wide variety of third-party tools, and which is interoperable with pan-EOSC activities via the FAIRsharing collaboration with OpenAIRE⁷.

Project Objectives

This deliverable has contributed directly to the following WP6 and WP1 objectives:

- a. Development of a personalized guidance to help RIs to follow and implementing the FAIR Principles (WP6).
- b. Advance the evolution of RI repository infrastructure for EOSC (WP1)
- c. Implementation of FAIR services and WP1 standards for RI data/data resources (WP1)

Detailed Report on the Deliverable

This deliverable summarises the work of WP6 to deliver a FAIRsharing Collection of data resources (and associated standards) to ensuring these resources are Findable (e.g. discoverable and citable

¹ <https://fairsharing.org>

² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4432029>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6208249>

⁴ <https://fairsharing.org/3513>

⁵ <https://fairsharing.org/organisations/839>

⁶ <https://fairsharing.org/organisations/3280>

⁷ <https://blog.fairsharing.org/?p=316>

via a DOI), Accessible (e.g. access methods to their data is clearly described), Interoperable (e.g. standards implemented are declared) and Re-usable (e.g. terms of use of the data are made explicit to users). FAIRsharing has been selected by WP1 as the project's registry of data resources and standards that are part of and used by research infrastructures in EOSC-Life, therefore the work is described in detail in:

- D1.2: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4432029>
- D1.3: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6208249>

The EOSC-Life FAIRsharing Collection of 133 records (as of Aug 2022) is publicly available on the FAIRsharing webpage:

<https://fairsharing.org/3513>

Delivery and Schedule

The delivery is delayed: No

Adjustments

Adjustments made:

None

